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Deliverable 2.5

State of Polarisation Sensing Comparison Report

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Abstract

This deliverable summarises the work done in the state of polarization (SOP) Task in WP2 of the SUBMERSE project up to 30.10.2025 in terms of the SOP interrogator devices deployment on selected, geographically separated submarine links and comparison of their performance and results.

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Executive Summary

The SUBMERSE project endeavours to develop a pan-European The aim is to build a system for continuous acquisition and dissemination of sensing data using submarine distributed fibre infrastructure, specifically designed to meet the needs of European research infrastructures. Using sensors attached to submarine fibre-optic communication cables, the project harnesses the capabilities of distributed acoustic sensors (DAS), state of polarisation (SOP), and polarimeter technologies. The system's instrumentation will be installed on at least three remote cable systems in Greece, Norway, and Portugal, each of which must allow the simultaneous acquisition of data generated by multiple devices.

This deliverable summarises the key results and lessons learned from Task T2.3 State of Polarisation, which developed, tested, and deployed sensor systems monitoring polarisation changes on selected submarine links within the SUBMERSE project. This document focuses on comparing the SOP devices deployed on various submarine links and the experiences with their deployment. Furthermore, this paper discusses the comparison of datasets from individual SOP sensing systems and their sensitivity and detection capabilities to record seismic and other events using optical fibers.

This deliverable is based on, further extends, and refines deliverable D2.4 State of Polarisation Design and Infrastructure Integration Model [1].

1. Introduction

This Deliverable logically follows on from the already submitted Deliverable D2.4 and further expands on it, especially in other areas of deployment and in the possibilities for comparing individual SOP monitoring technologies.

1.1 Report Objective

This Deliverable aims to compare the performance and deployment characteristics of various state-of-polarization (SOP) technologies across different geographical regions. The primary objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of other devices (polarimeters) that use SOP (e.g., Polbox, Novoptel Polarimeter PM1000, or SOP OTDR) and coherent transmission systems (e.g., Nokia CHM6 with DSP) for extracting SOP in diverse environments. The SOP is used as their primary source of information for recording external noise and vibrations. The Deliverable provides findings to identify the key parameters, challenges, and advantages associated with each technology and deployment location, proposing recommendations for future deployments and research in the field of SOP monitoring.

1.2 Deliverable Scope

The scope of the Deliverable is to encompass a detailed analysis of SOP-deployed technologies and their implementation in specific geographical areas. It covers the technical specifications and characteristics of various SOP devices, including different types of dedicated sensing devices as well as coherent transmission systems. The report summarizes additional findings to the Deliverable (D2.4) in the deployment locations in the Arctic Region (Svalbard: Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen) and adds new locations as the Mediterranean Region (Preveza – Crotone), and the Atlantic Region (Sines – Fortaleza). It examines the infrastructure requirements, specific on-site challenges, experimental verifications, and results obtained from these deployments. Furthermore, the report delves into the time synchronization aspects using White Rabbit Technology in certain locations and explores the potential of SOP OTDR on submarine cables, including its principles and utilization of amplifier backscatter signals.

1.3 Report Structure

The structure of this Deliverable starts with the comparison of State of Polarization technologies and their deployments. Following this introduction, Section 2 details the SOP deployed technologies, including various polarimeters and coherent transmission systems, along with their key parameters. Section 3 outlines the deployment locations and infrastructure requirements, covering regions such as the Arctic, Mediterranean, and Atlantic. Section 4 presents a comparative analysis of SOP technologies at these different locations, discussing

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deployed technologies, experimental results, infrastructure challenges, and specific deployment setups. Finally, Section 5 provides conclusions, summarizes key findings, addresses persistent challenges, and offers recommendations for future deployments and research. The report also includes a Glossary and References at the end of this document.

2. State of Polarization Deployed Technologies

To understand the data and, above all, the information value generated by individual SOP technologies, it is crucial to understand their technological parameters and the differences in how they record changes in the polarization state(s).

2.1 Polarimetric Solutions Deployed

Each device capable of SOP sensing has different technologies implemented, using different sampling rates and storing the Stokes vector values in different data formats.

The Polbox, developed by CESNET, is a pizzabox solution designed for long-term, continuous State of Polarization (SOP) acquisition. This 1U rack-mountable device can utilize an optical input signal from existing traffic, such as an Optical Supervision Channel (OSC), eliminating the need for additional laser sources or free data transmission channels. It records SOP data locally in Hierarchical Data Format version 5 (HDF5), a versatile format suitable for large datasets, with daily (compressed) data streams ranging from 6 to 13 GB. The Polbox supports external synchronization to remote storage and offers a continuous sampling rate of 20 kHz from four channels with 16-bit resolution. While the prototypes are not calibrated for absolute polarimetry, this limitation is deemed acceptable for sensing changes in SOP.

The Novoptel Polarimeter PM1000 is a sophisticated instrument capable of measuring all four Stokes parameters, which can be displayed on a Poincaré sphere or in oscilloscope mode. It offers a high polarization state sampling frequency of 100 MHz, allowing for the recording of up to 64 million polarization states. The device includes features such as averaging, triggering, and gating, with rich internal triggering possibilities based on intensity and SOP events. It supports real-time Poincaré sphere display and offers various normalization choices for Stokes parameters. The PM1000 is available as a desktop unit, a module card, and can be operated without an external computer.

So far, neither the SOP monitoring capable devices were intended to be deployed on long, transcontinental submarine links, due to the nature of the cascade of in-line optical repeaters. SOP OTDR (State of Polarization Optical Time Domain Reflectometer), on the other hand, is a technology with the potential for use on transcontinental, multi-amplified submarine cables. Unlike traditional OTDR methods, which primarily locate fiber cuts, SOP OTDR utilizes the backscatter signals from optical amplifiers along the cable to perform incoherent, SOP-only

measurements. This method allows for the detection of disturbances and events along the submarine cable, even though precisely locating the event can be more complex than with Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS). For the approximate event location, the trilateral per-span method is used.

2.2 Coherent Transmission System with SOP in DSP

The Digital Signal Processing (DSP) measurements are based on the CHM6-C8 transponders, which are based on the Integrated Coherent Engine 6 (ICE6) chip. These transponders, installed in the Ionian link, are line cards capable of providing a 1.6Tbps optical super channel. The transponders have 2 line-side interfaces, each corresponding to one super channel wavelength of up to 800 Gbps of traffic. Each of the optical engines can provide fast SOP readings of the SOP variation rate, the 4-dimensional Stokes vector, and the Jones matrix values, at a maximum rate of 10 ms, therefore 100 Hz.

This capability allows the network equipment to track polarization rotation changes in the optical channel for both sensing applications, as well as allowing the transponder to provide terrestrial backhauling of submarine cables. Fast SOP tracking speeds have little impact on the Q-factor of the transmission, only being effective for a very narrow Q-factor margin situation close to the FEC threshold, and therefore simultaneous sensing at 10 ms and production traffic are feasible. In low margin scenarios, the SOP measurement speed can simply be reduced.

At the maximum rate of 100 Hz, the sampling rate is enough to detect local and regional tectonic movement and earthquakes (requiring between 50 and 100 Hz of sampling rate), being even better suited for teleseismic earthquakes (requiring about 20 Hz).

The devices recover the SOP from the necessary polarization rotation tracking of the production traffic, which is implemented on the DSP module at the optical receiver. The extracted information poses no infringement or threat with regard to the contents of the production traffic, as it only requires the lowest-frequency component of the adaptive multiple-input multiple-output equalizer, far detached from optical carrier information or data contents.

2.3 Key Parameters and Characteristics of SOP Devices

The briefly introduced SOP optical sensing devices exhibit distinct technological parameters and methods for recording changes in polarization states. These differences are crucial for understanding the data and its information value. For instance, the Polbox has a fixed sampling rate of 20 kHz, using the HDF5 file format for data recording. Its sensitivity is from -35 dBm to +5 dBm, with -10 dBm as optimum. In contrast, the Novoptel Polarimeter PM1000 offers a significantly higher polarization state sampling frequency of up to 100 MHz, capable of recording up to 64 million polarization states (only 0.64 seconds at full speed), and provides advanced features like real-time Poincaré sphere display. However, it is using a feature called variable sampling rate, which is primarily intended to reduce the amount of data generated. Unfortunately, this functionality also significantly limits sensitivity and the possibility of comparison with other technologies. SOP OTDR, prototype solution by NOKIA Optical, on the other hand, is uniquely designed for transcontinental submarine links, employing the utilization of backscatter signals from optical amplifiers to perform incoherent, SOP-only measurements.

To understand how these varying characteristics directly impact their suitability for different deployment scenarios and the type of data they can provide is crucial for their correct use in individual cases of use. Key parameters such as sampling rate, data format, resolution, and measurement capabilities (e.g., measuring all four Stokes parameters) differentiate these technologies. While some devices prioritize continuous monitoring and large-scale data storage, others focus on high-frequency sampling and detailed polarization-state analysis. The choice of device often depends on the specific application, environmental conditions, and the required precision for sensing external noise and vibrations. Understanding these distinctions is fundamental for effective deployment and interpreting results from diverse SOP monitoring initiatives.

3. Deployment Locations and Infrastructure

Unlike the deliverable D2.4, there are two more locations where the SOP sensing systems have been deployed. The links have been chosen based on their distinct geographical location and fibre footprint seabed profile.

3.1 Overview of Deployment Locations

The brief introduction of the diverse geographical areas where SOP technologies are deployed. These regions include the Arctic (specifically Svalbard, encompassing Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen), the Mediterranean (Preveza – Crotona), and the Atlantic (Sines – Fortaleza). All optical links selected for the SOP deployment were carefully chosen not only for their geographically different location but also for their different parameters. The aim is to analyze the implementation of SOP-deployed technologies in these distinct environments, considering their unique infrastructure requirements and their specific adaptation to the capabilities of individual links.

3.1.1 Arctic Region: Svalbard (Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen)

The Arctic Region is represented by Svalbard (Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen), one of the most diverse geographical areas where SOP technologies are present. Here, the triple optical fibre sensing technologies are deployed, namely dual CESNET Polbox, dual Novoptel PM1000, and one Alcatel Submarine Networks (ASN) OptiDAS system. The Svalbard location was intentionally and carefully chosen for its environmental challenges as well as minimal negative environmental phenomena caused by human activity. The aim here is to analyze the implementation of these technologies in the long term within this distinct environment, taking into account the unique infrastructure properties and on-site challenges presented by the Arctic. Due to the fact that it was already described in detail in the previous (D2.4) Deliverable, it will not be discussed further in this document.

3.1.2 Mediterranean Region: Preveza – Crotone

This line is operated by islalink and includes a "Cable Lading Station" (CLS) at both ends (i.e., both on the Greek (Preveza) and Italian (Crotone) sides). Together with redundant terrestrial routes, islalink interconnects the cities on both peninsulas, like Milan, Rome, Athens, and Thessaloniki (see schematic picture below).

Fig 3.1.1 Islalink Preveza - Crotone and IT plus GR terrestrial links schematics Source: islalink.es

The link has in total of 24 unrepeated fibre pairs with a total length of 330km that can be equipped with any suitable vendor (open access model). The total attenuation of the link is greater than 55 dB. The cable is mostly laid (75%) on the seabed, more than 1000 m deep, which makes it suitable for environmental sensing purposes. The link is made of G.654.C Ultra Low Loss fibers. Final testing for the GÉANT dark fiber showed the submarine cable has a measured attenuation of 54.40 dB at 1550 nm.

Dark fiber on this line is operated by GÉANT in cooperation with NOKIA Optical, where the optical transmission system installed will be Nokia CHM6, 800G superchannels to be used in the DWDM spectrum (at frequencies 191.7, 191.8 THz [i.e., channels 17 and 18 according to ITU/T] in one direction and 191.8 and 191.9 THz [i.e., channels 18 and 19 according to ITU/T] in the other reverse direction), see detailed Optical Time Domain Reflectometry (OTDR) traces below.

Fiber	Estimated Attenuation at 1550nm (dB)	Measured Attenuation at 1550nm (dB)	Committed CD (ps/nm.km)	Measured CD (ps/nm.km)	Committed PMD (ps/km ^{1/2})	Measured PMD (ps/km ^{1/2})
15 W->E	55,05	54,40	18	16,527	0,1	0,008
16 W->E	55,05	54,40	18	16,379	0,1	0,009

Fig 3.1.2 Islalink OTDR Report

Source: GÉANT

3.1.3 Atlantic Region: Sines (Portugal) – Fortaleza (Brazil)

Fig 3.1.3.1 EllaLink Sines - Fortaleza Map Schematic

Source: EllaLink

The Sines (Portugal) – Fortaleza (Brazil) link is a trans-oceanic Ellalink submarine cable that utilizes 81 repeaters, with data being recorded at the Sines land station and each repeater along the line. SOP and Radio Frequency-State of Polarization (RF-SOP), referred to for simplicity below as SOP-Optical Time Domain Reflectometry (OTDR) data, is measured at each repeater, with the SOP-OTDR utilizing a direct-detect receiver and digital in-phase and quadrature (IQ) demodulation to measure the phase difference at each repeater, which can ultimately be converted to strains of each cable span. The overall deployment for this link faces deployment challenges related to repeaters and operator negotiations, while presenting a potential for SOP on the multi-amplified submarine cable, which uses backscatter signals from optical amplifiers for incoherent, SOP-only measurements.

Fig 3.1.3.2 EllaLink Seabed Profile

Source: EllaLink

The interrogating device deployed on the link is a Nokia (Infinera) patented prototype device called the Smart Sensing Unit (SSU) which could be described as an extremely powerful platform designed for the analysis of subsea optical signals, leveraging existing infrastructure to sense and precisely localize seismic, tidal, and cable events, thereby increasing the coverage of tsunami warning systems like DART II buoys.

The SSU-A hardware is a 2RU rackmount unit with an 8-core GPU and 2TB of onboard storage, featuring an

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embedded Web GUI for real-time and historical event visualization. It functions by comparing and analyzing direct and looped optical pulses from the CHM6S and subsea repeaters, utilizing a connected Polarimeter to stream SOP information and improve event localization accuracy, often using an eigenvalue method to pinpoint disturbances to a specific repeater or span. See the picture below for reference.

Fig 3.1.3 Infinera/NOKIA SSU Smart Sensing Unit Prototype

Source: Infinera/NOKIA

It combines simultaneously both SOP-OTDR and radio-frequency metrology. SOP-OTDR was introduced based on Rayleigh scattering in the late 80s, with a long history of development, but difficulties in implementation when using distributed scattering. In recent years, this has been addressed, and implementation in commercial products is well under way enabled by the shift towards monitoring the SOP from the High-Loss Loop Back (HLLB) supervision channel reflections. On the other hand, radio-frequency metrology, or Microwave Frequency Fiber Interferometry (MFFI) is a direct-detection technique akin in concept to coherent frequency metrology [4] proposed in [5] and expanded by [6] for EllaLink itself, with the aim to avoid the costly and complex low-linewidth lasers in favor of monitoring the phase of a MHz or GHz electrical carrier modulated over fiber, at the expense of resolution due to the larger wavelength.

3.2 Infrastructure Requirements for SOP Deployment

Compared to Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS), SOP has one huge advantage. It does not need dark fiber; it only needs one channel, or even only a divided part of the power (of course, in the detection range). The disadvantage is polarized signals, which are used by all coherent modulations, from 100G and up. In order to be able to monitor changes in polarization using direct detection schemes (most polarimeter-based approaches), the signal should be optimally unpolarized or fully polarized (Degree Of Polarization [DOP] close to 1). As of today, most multi-span reflective techniques deployed over EDFA amplified links are deployed in the OSC, as it is precisely the channel being artificially reflected by the FBGs for repeater health monitoring, and thus is already designed for decent power budget performances. Demonstrations such as [6], [7], [8] and [9] have all used the OSC channel for coherent frequency metrology, MFFI and OTDR, and OFDR, respectively. The use of the OSC channel has the following advantages as well:

1. No production data channels are used, allowing for full channel capacity utilization
2. The wavelength separation ensures sufficient isolation from production traffic
3. The OSC channel operation can be interrupted without production traffic downtime
4. There is a clear and defined separation between the sensing and the data transmission use-cases, which

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enables simpler data plan agreements and avoids involving third parties in confidentiality agreements

In contrast, polarization-multiplexed signals can only be analysed with the full implementation of a coherent DSP with an adaptive equalizer. This has been done a number of times since first proposed in [1], like in [9], and further explained in [10]. This does not use reflectometry, at the expense of measurand localization in standalone fibers, but has plenty of triangulation capabilities enabled by the ubiquity of the SOP tracking-capable transponders. SOP diversity using DSP at the receiver has been achieved in reflective measurements in [8] and [9], solving the signal fading reported in [7], and used in the transmitter in [2] for full localized birefringence characterization.

For Svalbard, the infrastructure consists of two parallel links with a total length of 255 km between Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen. The sensing setup constitutes a triple optical fibre sensing system, comprising dual CESNET Polbox devices, dual Novoptel Polarimeter PM1000 units, and one Alcatel Submarine Networks (ASN) OptoDAS system. The link also notably uses White Rabbit Technology for time synchronization, referencing an active hydrogen maser atomic clock in Ny-Ålesund. In the Svalbard case, the dark fibre is used for both DAS and SOP (which is the best configuration to have).

For the Mediterranean, the total length and attenuation are on the edge of what the SOP is able to detect (there is a pre-amp and booster configuration with Raman amplification). Thanks to lab tests, CESNET Polbox is able to detect changes in SOP even in this amplified configuration (taking advantage of signal amplification that preserves the polarization). After negotiation with NOKIA, the OSC (part of the power budget) will be used for SOP. Moreover, the SOP will be extracted from dual polarization modulation used by NOKIA CHM6 - a deployed coherent optical transmission system on the Preveza-Crotone link. Moreover, on the second fiber, the DAS system is installed for parallel event detection and subsequent data comparison.

The EllaLink operated transatlantic link, the situation is more difficult due to 81 in-line repeaters present on the link. Each span has a different length, and each repeater has a different level of noise added to the HLLB signal. A special device, capable of detecting from each per-span repeater utilizing signal phase shift (Infinera/NOKIA SSU), is deployed on the link. See the setup schematic below.

Fig 3.2.1 SSU Interrogator use of the High-Loss Loop Back signal

Source: EllaLink, [2]

4. Comparison of SOP Technologies at Different Locations

Each location is unique not only in terms of its parameters and geographical location, but also in the sensing systems deployed on a particular link. It is always a mix of several systems and technologies, so that the detected and recorded event can be multiple times confirmed and verified, and the sensitivity of individual sensing methods can be compared.

4.1 Svalbard (Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen)

This arctic location is equipped with all three technologies (DAS, Polbox, PM1000) as described above. Currently, we can provide only a comparison of DAS and Polbox, due to the fact that PM1000 was set to record with a variable sampling rate with a cap frequency of 48.8 kHz, but real sampling frequency varies by two orders of magnitude (hundreds of Hz to tenths of kHz), therefore it is impossible to show that data aligned with both other technologies. Recently, after the first data were released from PM1000, and this fact was observed, we updated the setup and started to measure with a fixed sampling frequency. At the time of writing this deliverable, new data with a fixed sampling frequency had not been released for analysis.

The Fig 4.1.1 shows a comparison of Polbox's channels aligned with DAS data, with a very strong trace of an event (small earthquake). What we can see is the situation where the intensity of the recorded trace of an event is not equal in all channels, and the amount of background noise is also very variable (see channels 0 or 3 vs channel 2). That depends on fiber physical properties like position, screw or strain, and also on the absolute polarization of the laser source. With any desired or unwanted cable movement, the suitability of a particular channel for event detection could be changed. This brings a challenge and a space for further investigation.

Fig 4.1.1 Comparison of Polbox's channels aligned with DAS data with a very strong trace of an event (small earthquake).

Because of the distinct intensities of particular channels of SOP data, the summary of all channels was performed as a first-hand preprocessing method. The results are shown in Fig 4.1.2 for both Polboxes. There is evidence that SOP is capable of recording weak submarine earthquakes, at least the first two most intense waves. The three very weak quake waves at 14:49:50, 14:53:30, and 14:56:20 are not visible in the SOP spectrogram data.

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Fig 4.1.2 Strong event (small submarine earthquake) is clearly visible on both Polbox (SOP) and DAS technologies.

The smaller sensitivity of SOP with comparison to DAS is evident from the following dataset, where weak disturbances around the cable were recorded by DAS technology (see Fig 4.1.3). These short-time events, also sharply enveloped in distance (the 1st and 3rd in time), could be some whale whistles. The 2nd event trace, the one a little bit blurred in distance, could be some extremely weak earthquake (shock in seabed) – it seems to be approximately 1000 m wide when it even occurred. None of these three events was recorded by SOP; they are probably too weak, and the power level is below the background noise. They were not visible by naked eye, also in any of the SOP channels, not only in the summed as shown in Fig 4.1.3 below.

Fig 4.1.3 Example weak disturbances caught by DAS are not detected by Polbox (SOP).

The known fact that DAS produces an overwhelming amount of data leads to setting a sampling frequency of ~300 Hz. From the Nyquist sampling theorem, the maximal frequency observable in our DAS data would be ~150 Hz. This fact limits the technology utilization for high-frequency events. On the other hand, Polbox sampling frequency is 20 kHz, and there we can catch traces of events up to 10000 Hz, which is ~66 times broader frequency range than only DAS can provide with a reasonable (~1TB/day) amount of data.

An example of such a high-frequency long-term (9 minutes) event caught by Polbox is depicted in Fig 4.1.4 – see the weak sinusoidal shape around 6900 Hz. The SOP spectrogram is clipped to a frequency range of 5200-6000 Hz for a clearer view. Currently, we have no idea what could be the origin of such an event. Besides that, in general, there are no traces of earthquake-like events in SOP data above ~100–200 Hz. There are nearly no visible traces in a submarine, a relatively “quiet” environment above 1000 Hz, with relatively rare exceptions, as in this example.

Fig 4.1.4 An example of a high-frequency long-term event caught by Polbox – weak sinusoidal shape around 6900 Hz with duration ~9 minutes.

4.2 Preveza – Crotone

This link is the most recently equipped from the SUBMERSE project links portfolio. It is equipped with the NOKIA CHM6 coherent optical transmission system, where DWDM superchannels for 1.6Tbps coherent transmissions are used. The link also uses the OSC channel for management, and it has been agreed that it, or a sufficient part of its power, will be used for the CESNET Polbox SOP sensing system deployment in the area.

As explained in sections 2.2 and 3.2, the device is capable of recovering the Stokes parameters, SOP rate of change, and Jones matrix with a time period of 10 ms, therefore 100 Hz, fulfilling the measurement range targeted by the majority of seismic sensing applications. The physical deployment of the transponders has been done already, and the start of the SOP data acquisition is expected to start in the upcoming weeks, as per the writing of this document. The partners from Nokia will assist with the installation and configuration of the production traffic and SOP acquisition, while the partners in Géant are already prepared to host the data acquired and its remote access. Here follow the current characteristics of the preliminary deployment, to be changed at the discretion of the production traffic users without expected significant impairment to the sensing operation:

Frequency L1	191750000
Frequency L2	191850000
Modulation	DPQPSK

Tab 4.2.1 Preveza - Crotone Optical Link Setup.

The Crotone-Preveza link is expected to provide insight into plenty of the SOP technique comparisons. On the one

hand, polarimeter-based systems have an unconstrained potential sampling rate and can operate at low input powers. On the other hand, most polarimeters are direct-detection based and therefore can recover well the Stokes parameters, but are insensitive to the common phase delay of X and Y polarizations, as well as to polarization dispersion loss and differential group dispersion between polarizations, which can be analysed using the transponders. Therefore, it is expected that the link will be capable of benchmarking both approaches and techniques with respect to one another against common phenomena.

The link is shorter than other links in the region, namely MedNautilus, and in the project, namely Ellalink, which will also provide insight into the effect of the span of fiber over the measurement.

With regards to the CESNET Polbox SOP sensing system using the OSC channel, the prospects for its usage are very positive as it provides a single polarization lightsource that is decoupled from production traffic in use and in frequency. The main time constraint to this point has been that, being a Raman amplified link, the equipment is provided by a third party other than Nokia, Islalink, and Géant, which delayed the testing and validation of the strategy. The final implementation details are currently being proofed by the partners of the operation center at Géant Networks, Nokia's own link supervision team, and equipment providers.

4.3 Atlantic Link (Sines – Fortaleza)

The NOKIA SSU prototype interrogator device is deployed at the EllaLink cable operator premises. It is using the HLLB signal from each repeater and using trilateration and phase shift for event detection and localization.

As per this report, the system is capable of providing clear spectral and time domain observations of relevant seismic and other environmental effects, even based on both SOP and RF OTDR. The presented observations are significant as the device uses cost-effective technologies that are readily capable of coexistence with production traffic and avoid costly ultra-low linewidth lasers and stabilizers, in favour of telecom-grade equipment.

4.3.1 SOP OTDR on Submarine Links

The key magic on the EllaLink transatlantic cable is the use of the supervision channel reflected by the HLLB. The HLLB serves a double function; it reflects the interrogator signal at the FBGs while also enabling the distributed reflections to pass-through, both with a consistent power, albeit with increasing optical noise. Therefore, the HLLB signal involves analyzing looped optical pulses and backscatter signals generated by the optical amplifiers within the subsea repeaters [3]. Intentionally developed devices like the Infinera SSU-A are deployed to compare and analyze these pulses, performing an incoherent, State of Polarization (SOP)-only measurement. This signal is processed using digital in-phase and quadrature (IQ) demodulation to measure the phase difference at each repeater, which can ultimately be converted into a measure of strain on each cable span between repeaters. The process allows for the detection of disturbances and events along the submarine cable, with the signal's characteristics, such as the noise added by each repeater, being a critical factor in the analysis. See internal per-repeater HLLB schematic below.

Fig 4.3.1 HLLB schematic in the submarine signal repeater

Source: ASN / EllaLink

4.3.2 Utilization of Amplifier Backscatter Signal

The raw data from the SSU-A located in EllaLink consists of the 4 Stokes parameters for each HLLB at synchronized timestamps, and the phase of the RF carrier for all HLLBs at synchronized timestamps as well. The Stokes parameters are obtained every 75 ms or 150 ms according to data write periods. The SNR of the measurement is constrained by the input power of the pulse to the fiber, which should be limited to avoid stimulated Brillouin Scattering. Therefore, the input power limitation leads to sparse errors in acquisitions at an approximate rate <2% of the obtained data that can be cleaned with a number of techniques. In the following graphs, the Median Absolute Deviation algorithm has been used to discard Stokes parameters that present discontinuities in time.

Fig 4.3.2 Original Stokes parameters from Repeater 1 in Ellalink, including outliers

Source: NOKIA

Fig 4.3.3 Original Stokes parameters from Repeater 1 in Ellalink, after outlier cleaning using a Z-factor of 4 and the Median Absolute Deviation figure Source: NOKIA

From Fig 4.3.2 and 4.3.3, the provided Stokes parameters, S0 is measured in W as it corresponds to the received optical power. S1 to S3 are already normalized with respect to S0 and are therefore unitless and constrained to values [-1, 1]. Then, the DOP can simply be computed as $\text{SQRT}(S1^{**2} + S2^{**2} + S3^{**2})$:

Fig 4.3.4 Degree of polarization over time for Repeater 35 Source: NOKIA

The DOP exhibits large periodic swings in time with an approximate period of 15 minutes, which should be studied carefully to properly understand its origin (Fig 4.3.4).

The average DOP over distance decreases from the first repeater onwards in a slight slope, as expected from the increase in unpolarized optical noise in the link, caused by the cascaded repeaters as seen in Fig 3.4.5:

Fig 4.3.5 a) Mean power over 12 hours returned by the several link repeaters. b) Same for the degree of polarization
Source: NOKIA

The main system measurand is, however, the normalized Stokes parameters, which are observably susceptible to a number of environmental effects, including the aforementioned periodic drift, even in the absence of reported seismic activity, see Fig 4.3.6:

Fig 4.3.6 Stokes parameters for Repeater 15 in the absence of seismic activity

Source: NOKIA

However, much larger swings can be observed in the presence of seismic activity, as seen in the following example at the position of Repeater 15, roughly located north of the Canary Islands, during the 6.9M earthquake. It is presented with the time-evolved Stokes parameters, as well as with the Poincaré sphere representation (normalized to unit radius), where time is color-coded, so a large swing with the same color is a perturbation localized in time, as combined in the Fig 4.3.9:

a) Fig 4.3.7

b) Fig 4.3.8

c)

Fig 4.3.9 a), b) Stokes parameters for Repeater 15 in the presence of seismic activity for the earthquake described in c)
Source: NOKIA

The outputs of the system can be analysed on time and in the spectral domain. The time domain can be readily explored with minimal processing by just considering the exact timestamps of the samples, given that they are delayed periodically and are presented later.

The spectral analysis consists of a signal processing previous to a regular spectrogram of the signal. What follows is the heuristic preliminary processing that has been used with the best success to visualize faint and definite time-evolving frequency components. Last to first, as seen in the Fig, 4.3.10, the operations follow:

Fig 4.3.10 Block diagram of data processing for Spectrogram computation

Source: NOKIA

The processing consists of a slow vector de-rotation is applied by calculating a sliding average over a 200s window, centering the differential SOP vector to north. This cancels the slow, environmental drifts (e.g., thermal or mechanical stress) whose frequencies are below 10 mHz, outside the targeted frequency components in this document. In the following figures, the color range has been compressed between the 99th percentile of data as the highest value, and 2 dB over the noise floor as the lowest value, computed from the median of the spectrogram samples. Then, re-sampling to a uniform sampling grid is applied, which can be done using cubic interpolation or Piecewise Cubic Hermite Interpolating Polynomial, with similar results. The spectrograms are obtained with standard parameters of overlap and with a Hamming window, and the following figures are the addition of spectrograms for parameters S1 and S2.

Fig 4.3.11 140 h spectrogram of Repeater 18, in logarithmic frequency scale, showcasing the tidal periodicity as well as the main seismic event spectral line, at the center time. Source: NOKIA

The above figure, Fig 4.3.11, is the 4-day-long (120h) spectrogram of Repeater 34, with the official time of the 6.9M earthquake in the Reykjanes Ridge serving as the center, and a good agreement with the observed peak in broadband frequency. Furthermore, in the frequency range of 0.2 to 0.5 Hz, narrowband spectral components can

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be observed periodically with an approximate repetition period of 12 hours and a duration of between half an hour and 3 hours, matching well with the semi-diurnal solar and lunar tidal periods. A big increase in the noise in the band of 100 mHz can be seen during the period of seismological activity.

The next spectrogram, Fig 4.3.12, obtained for repeater 14, shows the measurement on a linear y-axis with a broadband spectral component starting around 14:20, roughly 10 minutes after the declared seism time of 14:09.

Fig 4.3.12 4-hour close-up spectrogram of Repeater 25, in linear frequency scale, showing the aforementioned spectral line caused by the Reykjanes ridge seism of 6.9M, and the tidal spectral signature.

Source: NOKIA

While the presented measurements can be seen in a number of repeaters, not all detect known signals, and some do not contribute much more than noise, especially at the further end of the link. This can be addressed in a straightforward way by having a second sensing unit at the other landing station in Brazil, and work is underway to use polarization diversity at the transmitter to avoid fading due to the measurand effect being orthogonal to the local SOP, and gain through frequency-based techniques such as OFDM and frequency multiplexing.

The following combined Figure (Fig 4.3.13) showcases how the spectrograms for 3 groups of consecutive HLLBs (in vertical). It shows how the main seismic events are picked up by many of the repeaters in an alternating manner. For instance, it is clearly seen for repeaters 30 and 30, not for 32, a spectral line at the event start is seen at 33, and a clear one shortly after is seen at 34. It is better picked up by repeater 2 than its consecutives, and by repeater 55 than its precursors.

Fig 4.3.13: Several spectrograms in logarithmic frequency scale for consecutive repeaters (in rows) for separated stretches of the link (in columns).

The time-evolved signals can be seen in most repeaters, albeit with noise floor degradation, unlike spectrogram signals. In [10], it is shown that under linear assumptions, the mean square magnitude of the Stokes vectors is proportional to the integrated mean square strain along the fiber. Therefore, the summation of the variances of the normalized Stokes parameters is proportional to the strain at the optical fiber, and therefore ideally to the vibration to be measured through the Young's modulus. Thus, a simple moving variance of the measured Stokes parameters and their addition already provides a recognizable envelope signal of the seismic waveform. The following measurements are done with a moving variance window of 20 seconds, in blue, with just its sign inversion to complete the envelope visualization. A degradation of the noise floor is apparent, but the waveform is still distinguishable from it. A straightforward way to solve the issue is to have SOP interrogation at both ends of the link. The red dots correspond to cataloged repetitions in the same origin region of lower magnitude, which can explain the observed multiple peaks.

Fig 4.3.14: Time-evolved waveform envelopes per EllaLink ASN repeaters, and colorplot of the aforementioned for all repeaters, for the 6.9M seism in the Reykjanes Ridge Source: NOKIA

The last of the previous plots summarizes the results for all repeaters in a color plot in dB scale, showcasing the decrease in signal-to-noise ratio and showing clearly the main peaks expected from the seismic activity.

For the sake of completion, the following figure shows the same plots for a much lower magnitude, local earthquake of 4.3M without registered secondary events, in this case perfectly in sync with the official time of the earthquake, as no travelling delay is expected. This is in contrast with the previous 6.9M in Reykjanes ridge, which was detected

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around 9 minutes after its start. The observations match the expected range considering an approximate propagation speed of the detected waves at 4 to 7 km/s and a distance of 2900 km, thus an expected delay between 7 and 12 minutes.

Fig 4.3.15: Time-evolved waveform envelopes per EllaLink ASN repeaters, and color plot of the aforementioned for all repeaters, for the 6.9M seism in Fajã da Ovelha

The presented results are very promising, and plans to publish are underway by including further impairment and noise cleaning techniques, such as the singular value decomposition, with comparison to other state-of-the-art techniques. The presented results are already a relevant contribution to the technology commercialization efforts, already advanced, which is a testimony to the technology capabilities.

Analysis of the data from January 2025 revealed distinct characteristics and issues for the link's monitoring data. The phase data from January 18 showed a sudden change in sampling time and data style around 10:40, with the data before this time requiring pre-processing steps like de-spiking and phase unwrapping, and data after this time being assessed as potentially "useless." Full-Stokes vector measurements (S_0 , S_1 , S_2 , S_3) were also collected for each repeater and the landing station, exhibiting three types of fluctuations, including a quasi-periodic high-amplitude variation. A preliminary comparison of polarization angles between consecutive repeaters (RF01 and RF02) showed large differences, suggesting a potential problem in data reading, interpretation, or methodology for comparing SOP

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data from neighboring repeaters.

Analysis of data from 20th March 2025 shows similar characteristics; the sampling frequency varies from 0.485 Hz to 15.385 Hz, with a mean value of 11.078 Hz. The values of S0 from all repeaters are depicted in Fig 4.3.16. The first (S0R0) is approximately 5 times stronger than any of the rest, which is within acceptable limits.

Fig 4.3.16: Stokes' parameter S0 for all repeaters for the same time period of 24 hours.

What is not within acceptable limits is the DOP calculated from the data. Stokes parameters S1-S3 are in the range approximately. -0.32 to 0.38 (see Fig 4.3.17), and if we calculate $DOP = \sqrt{S1^2 + S2^2 + S3^2} / S0$ we obtain values from the range 8642.686 to 9452.866 (mean 9017.177), but from the definition, this should be constrained in the interval 0–1. This is directly caused by an imbalance of intensity of the S0 parameter (S0 is ~1000 times weaker than S1-S3).

Fig 4.3.17: Stokes' parameters S1, S2 and S3 for repeater #1.

Regardless of the mentioned challenges (variable sampling rate and probably incorrectly scaled metrics), we can investigate the SOP data as it stands. Fig 4.3.16. depicts the S0-S3 for each repeater during the selected period of time. On the left side of each row, there is a 3D plot where the X-axis is for time, the Y-axis is for the repeater, and the Z-axis shows the value of a particular S_i . The data were downsampled by a ratio of 10 for 3D plots. The same is shown as a 2D plot beside. Each visualization could be useful for showing different traces. The reference repeater #0 is omitted due to its outlier values; therefore, the 2D plots have only 81 rows.

Based on this data, we can say that ca. 12 events leave their traces visible as vertical columns in S1-S3 2D plots. It seems that such columnar traces are spread across all 81 repeaters (compared by naked eye) at least till sample ~ 650000 , so these events are probably related to something inside the optical beam (goes through the whole cable) – an internal event. Around the sample ~ 650000 , we can observe traces of increasing intensities of S3 on repeaters #1–#17, but for the rest of the repeaters, the intensity of S3 remains the same or even decreases. We hypothesize that these traces are related to something that happened near the first quarter of cable and did not spread so far along – an external event.

Fig 4.3.16: Each row shows a different view of the same Stokes parameter S_i on each repeater during the selected day. The color scales on 2D plots are not aligned for the same range due to the big gap between values for S_0 and others.

We can also investigate the signal in particular segments (from selected repeaters) from the perspective of the frequency domain in plots known as spectrograms. A spectrogram shows the behaviour of the frequency spectrum in a given time interval (X-axis). Such a spectrum is depicted in Fig 4.3.18, where nearly nothing is visible – it is a common case when only background noise is recorded. Weak traces at the bottom are visible at places corresponding to visible changes in columns of 2D plots in Fig 4.3.17. Also, some weak constant disturbances (at 0.5, ~1.2, ~1.7 Hz) are observable.

Fig 4.3.18: A spectrogram of the S3 Stoke parameter on repeater #11.

Very similar conditions are, for example, on the spectrogram from the S3 parameter on repeater #52, which is plotted in Fig 4.3.19. There is a clearly visible trace of an unknown event starting ~ 69000 th sec at 0.3 Hz. In general, we can only speculate about the origin of that event; one hypothesis is the micro-earthquake or seabed movement.

Fig 4.3.19: A spectrogram of the S3 Stoke parameter on repeater #52. See the trace of the event starting at approx 69000th second and having frequency ~ 0.3 Hz

5. Conclusions and Future Work

The project is still ongoing, and we expect to be able to extract SOP from the DWDM optical transmission system to compare it with the dedicated SOP sensing equipment. Moreover, we expect more data to be released from the Arctic area by Norway to be able to compare commercial and non-commercial SOP sensing systems alongside DAS in more detail.

This paper presents the results and findings from the comparison of SOP sensor deployments in different locations within the SUBMERSE project. Thanks to the parallel installation with DAS, we have the opportunity to compare the sensitivity of these systems and also recommend their suitability for deployment according to the use case and the capabilities of the given submarine line.

Challenges that still lie ahead include the possibility of long-term installation and sustainability even after the project is over, and comparing these methods with traditional, discrete subsea seismic sensors such as Ocean Bottom Sensors (OBS). Another, as yet unexplored area is how to properly handle the data generated by these systems and make them available to expert teams and groups, but also their use as early warning sources (e.g., in offshore environments). Unfortunately, automatic data filtering is not yet set up in a way that can be said with certainty that the system will not record anything that could, if made available to unauthorized users, compromise security

Finally, it should be mentioned that this area is still quite new and unexplored and it would be appropriate to conceptualize it, especially in terms of real-time data processing, optimization of the amount of generated data (i.e. whether it is possible to completely (and safely) exclude some frequency ranges from monitoring) or application and training of appropriate artificial intelligence models so that they can precisely predict, for example, seismic, life-threatening events,

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Glossary

ASN	Alcatel Submarine Networks
CESNET	Czech Education and Scientific Network
CLS	Cable Landing Station
DAS	Distributed Acoustic Sensor
dBm	Decibels relative to 1 milliwatt
DOP	Degree of Polarization
DSP	Digital Signal Processing
DWDM	Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing
GB	GigaByte
Gbps	GigaBit per Second
GÉANT	Pan-European Research and Education Network
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format version 5
HLLB	High-Loos LoopBack (Signal)
MFFI	Microwave Frequency Fiber Interferometry
nm	Nanometer
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology
OBS	Ocean Bottom Sensors
OCM	Optical Channel Monitoring
OSC	Optical Supervision Channel
OFDR	Optical Frequency Domain Reflectometry
OTDR	Optical Time Domain Reflectometry
RF	Radio Frequency
SOP	State of Polarisation
SSU	Smart Sensing Unit
SUBMERSE	Submarine Cables for Research and Exploration
WR	White Rabbit